

potentiometric titrations, the following mixtures keeping acetone : water ratio (v/v) 1 : 1 in 50 ml of the reaction solution, were titrated against carbonate free 0.2 M KOH :

- (A) 5 ml of 0.04 M HClO₄
 (B) Mixture (A) + 10 ml of 0.02M ligand solution (Penicillin-v)
 (C) Mixture (B) + 5 ml of 0.002M metal solution.

The ionic strength of the above solutions was maintained to 0.1 M by adding the required quantity of 1.0 M NaClO₄ solution. Correction for pH-measurements in 50% acetone-water system was done as described by Van-Uitert and Hass⁶ and Irving-Rossotti⁵.

On progressive addition of the alkali during the pH-titrations a precipitate was obtained in each case. The pH of precipitation in different systems being : ~4.25 with Ag(I), ~5.8 with Zn(II) and ~5.0 with Pb(II). Therefore, in these cases all the calculations have been done below the pH of precipitations. Further, with the use of very dilute solution (1 × 10⁻⁴ M) of the metals, possibility of the formation of polynuclear complexes may be ruled out.

Irving and Rossotti⁵ equations were utilised to calculate the values of $\bar{n}_A$, $\bar{n}$ and pL^- . The values of log K₁, log K₂ and log β₂ were recorded directly from the formation curves ($\bar{n}$ vs pL^-) and refined by the best least square fits (Table 1).

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS, PV-COMPLEXES

μ=0.1 (NaClO₄) ; a=Half $\bar{n}$ method ; b=Least Square method

Temp. °C	Method	Ag(I)		Zn(II)		Pb(II)		
		log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β ₂
20°	a	4.79	4.87	4.45	9.32	4.88	4.55	9.43
	b	4.78	4.92	4.45	9.37	5.02	4.54	9.56
30°	a	4.52	4.55	4.25	8.80	4.60	4.32	8.92
	b	4.42	4.60	4.28	8.88	4.68	4.28	8.96
40°	a	4.16	4.24	3.93	8.17	4.32	4.03	8.33
	b	4.21	4.26	3.70	8.14	4.37	3.90	8.36

The conductometric and potentiometric (pH) titrations and the values of $\bar{n}$ (≈2) confirmed the formation of ML and ML₂ complexes—with Pb(II) and Zn(II), and only 1 : 1 (M : L) complex with Ag(I). (The maximum value of $\bar{n}$ ≈ 1 in this case.)

A perusal of Table 1 clearly indicates that the order of stability varies as : Ag(I) < Zn(II) < Pb(II). The electronic configurations of Ag(I), Zn(II) and Pb(II) being 4d¹⁰, 3d¹⁰ and 5d¹⁰, 6s² respectively. The greater stability of Zn²⁺ (3d¹⁰) complexes over that of Ag⁺ (4d¹⁰) may be expected in the light of the greater ionic charge and the smaller radius (i.e., the higher values of e²/r ratio) of Zn²⁺. The order of

stability for Zn(II) and Pb(II) complexes, on the basis of electronegativity, ionic size and ionisation potentials, should have been Zn(II) > Pb(II), but the order obtained in this investigation is reverse, i.e., Pb(II) > Zn(II). This seems, probably, due to 52 unit greater nuclear charges in Pb over Zn, which result in the higher values of e²/r ratio for Pb—giving greater stability to its complexes.

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Ceric-Benzilic Acid System as Redox Initiator in the Aqueous Polymerization of Methylmethacrylate

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THE use of ceric salts in combination with various organic reducing agents such as alcohols, aldehydes, acids and amines as redox initiators for vinyl polymerization has received much attention recently¹⁻⁴. It was thought that the use of an α-hydroxy acid with ceric salts will be an efficient initiator system. Some preliminary observations made with ceric sulphate-benzilic acid redox system in the aqueous polymerization of methylmethacrylate (MMA) are recorded in the present communication.

Experimental

All the reagents employed were of analytical grade. The polymerization experiments were carried out in the dark at ambient temperature under deaerated conditions (under nitrogen) and at a fixed acid concentration. Polymerization rate (R_p) was followed gravimetrically and degree of polymerization ($\bar{P}_n$) was measured viscometrically⁵. Palit's dye tests⁶ were applied for the detection of polymer endgroups.

Results and Discussion

Some important results are shown in Table 1. Ceric salt alone can initiate the polymerization of MMA, but the presence of benzoic acid considerably increased R_p , being proportional to the acid concentration. There was a slight reduction in $\bar{P}_n$ with increasing benzoic acid concentration. With increasing ceric ion concentration R_p remained practically unaffected, but there was a sharp fall in $\bar{P}_n$. Both R_p and $\bar{P}_n$ decreased with decreasing MMA concentration.

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF AQUEOUS POLYMERIZATION OF MMA WITH CERIC-BENZOIC ACID SYSTEM*

[Ce ⁴⁺] M × 10 ³	[Benzoic acid] M × 10 ³	[MMA] M	R_p mol l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹ × 10 ⁶	$\bar{P}_n$
1.27	Nil	0.094	0.0487	4631
1.27	4.59	0.094	4.74	3816
1.27	3.06	0.094	3.18	4065
1.27	1.53	0.094	1.80	4329
3.81	1.53	0.094	1.77	2536
12.70	1.53	0.094	1.82	1083
1.27	1.53	0.047	0.83	2734
1.27	1.53	0.019	0.36	1652

* [H₂SO₄] = 10⁻³ M and Temp. 30°.

Graphical plotting of these data shows that R_p is approximately proportional to the monomer as well as the benzoic acid concentration, but independent of ceric ion concentration.

Palit's dye test⁶ demonstrated the presence of hydroxyl endgroups⁷ in all the polymer samples, but carboxyl endgroups⁸ were absent.

These results suggest that the ceric ions participate in both initiation and termination reactions and that the initiating radicals contain only hydroxyl groups and no carboxyl groups. On the basis of our preliminary findings and the knowledge of the reported⁹ reaction of benzoic acid and ceric ions, the following mechanism of initiation is tentatively suggested.

where M represents the monomer.

That the hydroxyl endgroups in the polymer is not due to oxidation of water by ceric ions, was

proved by the fact that the polymer samples prepared in dimethyl sulphoxide medium also showed the presence of hydroxyl endgroups. Further work is in progress.

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Extractive Photometric Determination of Iron(III) with N-Hydroxy-N, N'-diarylbenzamidines from Thiocyanate Solutions

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N-Hydroxy-N, N'-diarylbenzamidines, newly synthesised organic reagents having monobasic and bidentate functional grouping¹⁻⁴ reacts with iron(III) in thiocyanate medium giving water insoluble red-orange mixed-complexes. The mixed-complexes are extractable into benzene with ϵ , 1.0-1.2 × 10⁴ l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 460-465 nm. Iron(III)-thiocyanate method⁵ is commonly used for determination of iron(III), but this method suffer with a number of analytical factors such as time of standing, thiocyanate concentration, non-linearity of Beer's law, etc. However, these factors are overcome in proposed mixed thiocyanato method. The selectivity and sensitivity of iron(III)-N-hydroxyamidine-thiocyanate method may be compared to other established methods⁶. The present paper reports the extractive-photometric determination of microgram quantities of iron(III) as thiocyanato mixed-complexes with seven newly synthesised N-hydroxyamidines. The method is applicable to determine iron in ores,